

INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN CRIMINAL LAW DISPUTE RESOLUTION THROUGH RESTORATIVE JUSTICE AND MEDIATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6350971>

Mukhammadyusuf Alijonov

*3rd year student of faculty of "Criminal justice" of
Tashkent state university of law,
Uzbekistan, Tashkent*

Annotation: *This article represents the analysis of foreign practice of mediation in the resolution of criminal law conflicts. As the victim-offender mediation is known more common part of the "restorative justice", its implementation and mechanism in some developed countries via legal acts analyzed by this approach.*

Key words: *crime; restorative justice; mediation; victim; offender; adult; juvenile justice.*

As the analysis of the legislation of many foreign countries shows, currently, a full-fledged legal institution of mediation has developed, which consists in granting the parties the right to their own active actions to resolve the conflict (dispute) that has arisen between us on mutually beneficial or, at least, on mutually acceptable terms for them, with the participation of a mediator as a neutral and impartial person assisting the parties in reaching an agreement.

This institution has an intersectoral character and is successfully used not only in the practice of settling disputes arising from civil, family, labor, corporate and other private law relations, but also conflicts caused by criminal behavior. First of all, for a general idea of foreign colleagues about mediation in criminal conflicts, it is necessary to refer to its definitions in foreign official and scientific publications, taking into account the innovative nature of foreign experience in this field.

The document of the organization "Mediation UK, 1994" (Great Britain) contains the following definition: "Mediation: a process in which the victim(s) and the offender (s) communicate with the help of an impartial third party, either directly (face to face) or indirectly through a third party, allowing the victim(s) to express their feelings and talk about needs, and the offender(s) to assume obligations and act in accordance with them" [1].

In the "Explanatory Memorandum" of the Council of Europe to the "Recommendation on Mediation in Criminal Cases" (1999): "Mediation in criminal

cases is defined as a process through which the victim and the offender can get the opportunity to voluntarily take an active part in solving problems caused by a crime with the help of an impartial third party or mediator" [2]. M. Leibman defined mediation (mediation) between a victim and a criminal as a process in which an impartial third party helps the victim(s) and the criminal(s) to communicate, directly or indirectly, which can lead to greater mutual understanding between both sides, and often to tangible compensation for the damage caused [3].

Many programs of reconciliation of victims and criminals and settlement of criminal law conflicts (mediation, justice circles, public councils and conferences and other restorative practices) have been developed and used in foreign legal practice. At the same time, mediation is the most popular procedure.

In the scientific and analytical literature, repeated attempts have been made to systematize the forms and models of mediation used in foreign countries in criminal cases. Thus, in the Explanatory Note to Recommendation No. R (99) 19, developed by the Committee of Experts on Mediation in Criminal Cases (PC-MP), it is noted that the practice of mediation in criminal cases can take different forms, which are often combined with each other, for example: [4]

- * exchange of opinions about the incident for a better understanding between the victim and the offender;

- * the offender's apology and voluntary acceptance of the obligation to make amends for the harm caused to the victim;

- * the offender's voluntary consent to take some other action, for example, to work for the community or to participate in a rehabilitation program ("indirect compensation for harm");

- * resolution of any conflict between the victim and the offender or between their families or friends;

- * adoption of a program of coordinated sanctions and decisions that can be offered to the court as a recommended sentence or court order.

Mediation can be carried out by professional mediators or specially trained volunteers. Mediation can be carried out under the auspices of a criminal justice body or on the basis of an independent local community body. The parties to mediation can be the victim and the offender (as in the "classic" form of mediation between the victim and the offender), but also their relatives, members of the local community and representatives of criminal justice authorities (as in family and community conferences). But, despite some differences in forms, in all cases, the impartiality of the mediator and the voluntary participation of the parties in the program are essential.

On the basis of these forms of mediation in criminal cases, in foreign countries, taking into account national socio-political and legal traditions, various models of mediation have developed, which are often interfaced, combined with each other. At the same time, the main models of criminal law mediation are as follows:

1. Informal mediation - is carried out by employees of criminal justice bodies in the course of their normal work. This may be a prosecutor inviting the parties to participate in an informal settlement of the conflict with the intention to terminate the prosecution if a satisfactory agreement is reached.

2. Traditional village or tribal gatherings are an ancient institution, suggesting that the entire community meets to resolve disputes and criminal conflicts between its members, is still common in less developed countries and rural areas.

3. Mediation between the victim and the offender - assumes that the parties (while the number of both offenders and victims is not limited) meet in the presence of a specially appointed mediator leading the meeting selflessly or for a fee.

4. Compensation negotiation programs - exist solely in order to determine the amount of material or other possible compensation for the damage caused, which the offender will have to pay to the victim on the basis of a court decision.

5. Public courts - involve the transfer of criminal cases by the prosecutor's office or courts to the local community for consideration according to the rules adopted in it, which are more flexible and lack of formalism, often include elements of mediation and negotiations.

6. Family and community conferences are another example of community involvement in the criminal justice system (developed in Australia and New Zealand). It is supposed to meet not only the victim and the offender, but also the relatives and friends of the offender, representatives of institutions such as the police and justice authorities for youth and minors, as well as sometimes supporters of the victim.

The most common classification, which also has an important criminal legal significance, is the division of mediation (mediation), based on its relationship with the traditional criminal justice system into three basic models [5].

Let's consider the experience of foreign countries on the use of mediation in criminal cases in more detail from the point of view of the criteria we have identified.

1. The range of crimes for which mediation is possible. When developing the concept of mediation for the resolution of criminal law conflicts, the question of which categories of crimes the mediation procedure is possible is of primary importance. As a rule, mediation is used in cases of minor crimes against the

person and property. Some countries provide in their laws those categories of crimes that are not subject to mediation. Often, the applicability of mediation is limited to a certain type or amount of punishment provided for the commission of a crime. The approaches of different countries to solving this issue differ: some States limit the range of such crimes, others allow the use of mediation procedures in relation to any criminal acts. Thus, according to the provisions of the Law on Mediation (No. 21/2007) of **Portugal**, criminal cases of crimes against the person or property belonging to the category of cases of private prosecution, which are punishable by a fine or imprisonment not exceeding five years, can be submitted for resolution through this procedure. The crimes subject to the mediation procedure include, in particular: verbal insults, minor bodily injuries, robbery, fraud, slander. At the same time, mediation cannot be applied in cases of crimes against sexual freedom and against persons under the age of 16 [6].

Unlike Portugal, in **England and Wales**, cases of crimes of almost any category, including those against persons who have repeatedly committed crimes, can be submitted for settlement through mediation [7].

In the **United States**, mediation programs between victims and criminals, originally used in cases involving property crimes and minor assaults, are becoming increasingly widespread in relation to a wide range of crimes and are now being used even in relation to serious violent crimes. The trend of mediation development here is to expand the scope of such programs [8].

2. The identity of the criminal as a participant in a criminal legal conflict.

As a rule, foreign countries take into account the data on the person who committed the crime (age, repetition of crimes) when deciding on the use of mediation. As noted above, many countries follow the path of initially applying mediation only in cases of juvenile crimes, and then extend this procedure to adult criminals.

A typical example is the development of mediation in **Portugal**, which began with the sphere of juvenile justice. There, mediation for the resolution of criminal law conflicts first appeared in the Law regulating the Use of Coercive Measures of educational influence to minors who have committed a crime (Educational Guardianship Law No. 166/99 as of September 14, 1999). This law applies to minors between the ages of 12 and 16. In relation to adults who have committed illegal acts, mediation in Portugal appeared relatively recently, in 2007. Mediation for the resolution of a criminal law conflict or the so-called Victim and Offender Mediation (Victim Offender Mediation) in Austria was initially used in cases of juvenile crimes (it was provided for by the Law on Juvenile Justice of 1989), and in 1999 it began to be provided for adults [9].

3. Criminal-legal consequences of the mediation procedure. For example, according to the Finnish Law on Reconciliation (No. 1015/2005), the achievement of a mediation agreement, i.e. reconciliation of the parties, enshrined in the relevant document, as well as the fact of a person's willingness to participate in the procedure, may entail various legal consequences: from the termination of proceedings in the case (in the case of minor crimes) to the mitigation of the sentence imposed or refusal to appoint it at all.

In the **USA**, in cases involving serious violent crimes (murders, sexual assaults), the conclusion of a reconciliation agreement does not lead to the termination of the criminal case, but can only be recognized as a mitigating circumstance [10].

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